

TRANSLATION ISSUES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN SPORT TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation. The article investigates the challenges in translating sport phraseological units and terms in sport terminology. It states that phraseology has been in the centre of attention of linguists since the beginning of the 20th century. The works regarding phraseology by many linguists such as V.V.Vinogradov's, E.D.Polivanov's, B.A.Larin's and others have been studied by the author and the methods of translating phraseological units suggested by J.P.Vinay, J.Darbelnet, K.Musaev, G. Salomov and N.Christian have been thoroughly considered. We mention influences of English sport phraseological units and terms in Uzbek sport terminology. They are mainly considered to be the product of sport commentators' intelligence. We also write about the importance of the context while translating phraseological units. He claims that depending on the context the translation of the same phraseological units may differ. The author also explains the differences between sport phrases and terms using various sport matches. We come to the conclusion that the above-mentioned methods are very important while translating phraseological units. The importance of phraseological units, namely sport phrases and terms in the communication process relating to sport terminology has been stated in the article as well.

Keywords: phraseology, phraseological units, terms, sport terms, sport phrases, equivalent, pragmatic, cultural, linguistic and text-specific problems translation, dictionary.

1 INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, there are such phraseological units that create the expressiveness and imagery of speech, and their appearance is strongly connected with people's views and attitudes towards objects and events in objective existence. Soviet linguist E.D.Polivanov was the first person who worked on the matter "phraseology as a linguistic discipline". He wrote in his work on phraseology: And now there is a need for a special department that would be commensurable with the syntax, but at the same time includes in itself not the general types, but the individual meanings of the data of individual (lexical) meanings of individual words [Поливанов Е.Д., 1958: 67].

The next scientist, who investigated the same issue, was B.A.Larin. He argued that this branch of linguistics is still at the stage of registration as a full-fledged science, but he pointed out that, it is impossible to deny the necessity of singling out such a discipline. Professor B.A.Larin under the subject of phraseology demonstrated indissoluble, stable combinations, that is, close unity of several words, expressing a holistic view [Larin B.A., 1956: 22].

"The study of the relationship between terminology and phraseology is one of the new and urgent issues of modern linguistics" [Федуленкова Т.Н., Иванов А.И., Куприна Т.В., 2009: 23].

We know that phraseological units and stylistic devices are such tools that increase the effectiveness of speech. Just as the study of phraseological and stylistic problems occupies an important place in the structure of linguistic and artistic text translations, today the study of special aspects of linguistics, in particular, from the point of view of terminological systems, is gaining relevance.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- While most of the English sport terms and phraseological units that have become popular from sports terminology continue to be expressed in their original form without changing their form, some phraseological units and terms are also being used in new meanings in Uzbek sport terminology. Phraseological units and terms in Uzbek sport terminology with such a stylistic color create some difficulties in the translation and interpretation of terms and phraseological units in the field of sports.

- In the field of linguistics, the role of translation is incomparable in imagining the source of the original language in accordance with the times, that is, according to the requirements of the time. Therefore, mastering the secrets of artistic skills of the translation field in every way, presenting a colorful resource related to a foreign language in an authentic manner, and realizing the various meanings reflected in the words according to the use of words in this delicate process, is a proof of how

complex, responsible and unique creative process the translation field is.

- Translation scientist K.Musaev wrote: “The need to accurately interpret the relationship between form and content in translation imposes on the artist the task of choosing alternative language and speech units that can creatively reflect the tasks of all linguistic and stylistic tools that create the artistic sophistication and national character of the work” [Мусаев К, 2005: 4].
- In addition, G.Salomov has repeatedly emphasized that translation is a process directly related to consciousness. In particular, he wrote: “The reason for the possibility of translating from one language to another is that, although the peoples of the world speak different languages, their laws of thought are the same” [Саломов Г, 1976: 285].

3 ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The role of translation in the field of terminology is important, and one of its tasks that should be studied is the process of “translational equivalence”. The concept of equivalent is considered one of the central concepts in the field of translation, and it is appropriate to say that the solution of semantic translation problems in the language, the study of the content aspect, is directly related to this process.

This lexical unit appeared in the English language in the 15th century, and it entered the Latin language in this century. The lexical form of that period was “aequivalentem” and was presented to general consumption in such meanings as equal in value, power, or effect [www.etymonline.com]. In today's modern dictionaries, including the Oxford dictionary, it is used in the sense that is equal in value, meaning or purpose to something else. The explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language give two different definitions regarding the concept of equivalent. 1) noun. something else that is equal to or in some way suitable with something and can replace it; 2) adjective. equal, suitable and replaceable

[Oxfordonlinedictionary.com].

It should be noted that some sources use the term alternative instead of the term equivalent. However, the explanatory dictionary provides three main definitions of the term alternative 1) opposite, contradictory; 2) in the opposite direction; 3) answerable. It is precisely the third definition that suits us.

Equivalent is the matching of the meanings of the language units of two or more languages, that is, the semantic harmony of the language units in the language systems being compared. Similarity between the source language and the translation language in terms of

content, structure and function is considered equivalent (alternative)[Рахимов Ф, 2016: 52].

Based on the sources, it can be said that the translator may face translation difficulties that are not related to his competence in providing equivalents during the translation process. This is why Christian Nord divides the problems into four categories, i.e. a) pragmatic, b) cultural, c) linguistic and d) text-specific problems. Solving these problems requires the translator to use a specific translation strategy.

A) Pragmatic aspects. In our work, we analyzed the descriptions recorded by the scientist. Pragmatic issues in translation are related to the speech activity of a person, and it is a department that studies the meaning of linguistic units in communication. Pragmatic equivalent in the process of translation (comparatively simultaneous interpreters are more likely to encounter) is a process that occurs with a certain term or neologisms in the existing terminological field. It is natural that a complex, complicated speech situation arises in connection with this process in translation. For example: nashball - neologism creates difficulties for the translator in the process of communication. The reason is that it takes some time to find the equivalent of this new lexical item. This is because the term is not commonly used in sport terms. Nashball is a fast-paced and athletic team sport inspired by the simplicity and free flow of soccer (football) incorporating ball handling used in volleyball and fistball (faustball – german language). Nashball allows ball contact with the entire body, has simplistic rules, minimal equipment, and accommodates players of any size and athletic background. Such complications: Polocrosse is a team sport that is a combination of polo (it is a ball game played on horseback, a traditional field sport and one of the world's oldest known team sports [http://www.argentinapolo.com/polohistory.html]. and lacrosse (it is a team sport played with a lacrosse stick and a lacrosse ball. It is the oldest organized sport in North America) [Britannica Educational Publishing (2015). Lacrosse and Its Greatest Players. Britannica Educational Publishing. pp. 10–12. ISBN 978-1-62275-593-6]. It is played outside, on a field (the pitch), on horseback. Each rider uses a cane or fibreglass stick to which is attached a racquet head with a loose, thread net, in which the ball is carried. The ball is made of sponge rubber and is approximately four inches across. The objective is to score goals by throwing the ball between the opposing team's goal posts [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polocrosse].

It is understood that the modern translator perfectly mastering the information about the object and subject of the original in the process of translation practice

eliminates the arising (pragmatic) complications. The best way for new terms and neologisms is to explain them.

B) Cultural aspects. The second classification noted by the scientist is the process of translation, taking into account cultural aspects, and it is the translation of terms and relations between the language and cultural concepts specific to a particular nation. In addition, within the cultural aspects of translation, the translator needs to find and translate the equivalent of cultural concepts of different languages, including cultural models, cultural categories, and cultural metaphors based on the characteristics of that language. For example: The Achilles Heel for Runners: With the nature of the last few years, many of us have had interruptions to our exercise routines. For runners especially, this can significantly increase the risk of injuries. This phrase which mentioned above that is mainly used running sports, but also is a medical term which is namely the Achilles tendon or heel cord, also known as the calcaneal tendon, is a tendon at the back of the lower leg, and is the thickest in the human body [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Achilles_tendon].

The origin of this term is related to in Greek mythology. The fact that it has no equivalent in another language is a linguistic lacuna.

Several complex issues arise when translating the cultural aspects of field terms from a specific source. An example of this is the term lacuna, which was brought to linguistics by Canadian scientists J.P.Vinay and J.Darbelnet, who noticed such problematic situations. Scientists define this term as follows: “a lacuna phenomenon occurs in places where a word in one language does not have an alternative in another language” [Vinay J.P., Darbelnet J., 1958: 78]. Lacuna is often seen as lacking unit, zero verbal nomination, absent meaning, nonexistent concept in one language, culture and society which with no corresponding equivalent [Szerszunowicz J. Lacunarity, lexicography and beyond: integration of the introduction of a linguo-cultural concept and the development of l2 learners’ dictionary skills. *Lexicography*, 2(1), 2015. 101-118 pp. DOI: doi.org/10.1007/s40607-015-0015-6].

In the 70s of the last century, the components of linguistics, such as linguo-cultural studies, translation studies, linguo-country studies, developed, and the term lacuna became popular. In various studies, the concept of lacuna is called by such terms as gap, lacuna, antonyms, gaps, lacunae or white spots on the language map, untranslatable words, no alternative, zero word, no alternative or background lexicon, random lacunae, untranslatable lexicon [Usmonova Sh, 2014: 79]. Issues related to the equivalent of terms in translation are

prominent in the works of P.Newmark in the field of translation. He has often noted that cultural equivalent and visual equivalent are important among translation tools [Newmark P, 1991: 35].

C) Linguistic aspects. Although finding and providing an equivalent through these aspects seems to be a relatively easy process, it is natural that its specific aspects make it difficult for the translator. For example, “hot dog” is literally translated into Uzbek as “issiq it”(hot dog), while there is no equivalent of this phraseological unit in the Uzbek language. Such phraseological units are also used within the field of English sports, which have mainly passed into this field from the social lexical layer. Hot dog – murakkab mashqlar va hatti-harakatlarni tezlik bilan bajardigan epchil, chaqqon sportchi (chang‘i sport turida) (Look at that guy hot dogging all over the place! – Sen u bolaga bir qaragin, chang‘ida qanaqa murakkab hatti-harakatlarni bajarayapti!)

D) Features specific to the text are one of the complex processes in the translation process. First of all, it is necessary to analyze the text with the lowest level of semantic similarity with the original text. Because they do not come across similar themes or devices. The formal connection between the original text and its translation is not noticeable, but there is a meaningful connection.

According to A.V.Kunin, the phraseological units mean the understanding that the meanings of their structural components are interrelated with the synchronic aspect [Кунин А.В, 1964: 58]. In this meaning, phraseological units appear in a form in accordance with the spirit, mentality, life experience and tradition of the nation, carry a portable meaning based on words with a special meaning along with the meanings and structural construction of the components contained in it.

In the field of sports, there are such phraseological units that undergo certain evolutionary periods. When analyzed historically, the process of gradual development of such phraseological units emerges. One such example is the playbook unit. Historical sources show that the British have long been considered pious people, and almost all families had books that defined, demonstrated, and explained their religious practices. This book is called the pray(er) book.

It has been used in the sports field since 1965 in a figurative meaning. In the sport, the playbook is a guide that expresses the strategic instructions of the coach. Currently, there are written, magnetic board, and electronic versions of them. Playbook in Uzbek is used as a neologism by sports journalists without the article. These phraseological units are often observed during

comments by English-speaking journalists. For example: Being in coach Shanahan's system and learning the playbook, that's really the hardest thing (Dieter Kurtenbach) - Shanaxan tizimida murabbiylik qilish va o'yin kitobini o'rganish, bu haqiqatan ham eng qiyin narsa.

4 ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In fact, dealing with the translation of phraseological units is one of the complex and significant creative areas of translation practice. In their translation, the translator's talent, ability, ability to understand and feel words and imagery, impressiveness at a high level are shown. It should be noted that in the process of giving Uzbek alternatives of English phraseological units, or in the process of translation, there are more words in Uzbek than in the original language, but phraseological units in the field of sports appear more compact compared to the original language when they are characterized as terms or neologisms.

Based on the results of the research analysis, we were convinced that the English phraseological units used in the Uzbek language as terms or neologisms are used by experts and journalists in two different ways at the same time, and what is noteworthy is that one does not negate the other. Including:

- 1) by using an alternative in translation;
- 2) by directly using the original language form.

Examples of such units include phraseological units such as English man of the match, golden boy. Man of the match is widely used in team sports. In the original language, it is used to express the best player among the participants of the game, the most effective, profitable, distinguished from others by his actions.

A (non-symbolic) award is usually established for players deemed worthy of the title. For example: Rooney was voted a man of the match - Runiy eng yaxshi o'yinchi deb topildi [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wayne_Rooney].

This unit, man of the match, is used unchanged by journalists commenting on the latest games in Uzbek language, but in Uzbek language there is also the term eng yaxshi o'yinchi (in the game) as an alternative to this phraseological units. During the Uzbek Commentary, we observed such situations that even in the same sentence, there are cases where one is used as an explanation for the other. For example: Agar jiddiy o'zgarish bo'lmasa, Luka Modrich man of the match ya'ni eng yaxshi o'yinchi deb topiladi (Davron Fayziyev: Real Madrid - Chelsea, 3:0) [FutbolTV], Kibo Kurtua ushbu to'p uzatishi bilan keskinlashtiruvchi va riskli vaziyatni o'z jamoasi uchun keltirib chiqarishi mumkin edi (Davron Fayziyev: Real Madrid - Manchester City, 1:0) [SportTV].

Golden boy - this phraseological unit is multi-functional in English. The use of this unit in several figurative senses can cause complications in the attribution process. For example: 1) golden boy - the name of the traditional award established by the football association for the best player under the age of twenty in world football, for example: 2018 Golden Boy award is given to Isco (Malaga) – 2018 Golden Boy sovrini **Isco ga** (Malaga) topshirildi [[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Golden_Boy_\(award\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Golden_Boy_(award))]. 2) golden boy - the name of the players who worked in a certain national team or club based on their behavior and characteristics. Former German national team player Oliver Birkhoff was named the golden boy for his goal scored in extra minutes at the 1996 European Championship (there was a golden ball rule at the time). The former player of the England national team, Paul Scholes, was called by this name on social networks because of his strong influence on the result of the game due to his color appearance and skills. Many examples of players with this name can be given. 3) golden boy - sportsmen bought to the team at a high price, but who could not prove themselves, are ironically called golden boy by fans and specialists [White P, 2005: 320]. In the Uzbek language, the term "golden boy" is used both directly and alternately.

In general, regardless of the type of phraseological units, they cannot be literally translated from one language to another. If they are translated literally, they lose their figurative meaning. It is appropriate to translate the phrases according to the context in which they appear and the original version, internal laws and features of the translated language. For example: sehrlı tayoqcha – magic(al) stick, so called because the player of our national team, Anvar Soliev, scored a goal after coming off the bench; kulib turgan iblis – smiling devil, former player and head coach of Manchester United club, Olle Gunnar Solskjaer, was named after the combination of smiling goals and the word "devil", which is the symbol of the club; yulduzlik kasali – used for players who have become cyborgs due to their popularity (and as a result have lost their skills); o'lim guruhi – the group of death is used to describe a group in a tournament (such as the World Cup) that is made up entirely of teams who are considered very strong. Example: "Brazil 2014 served up a number of groups that were considered competitive enough to be described as "Groups of Death". One such example was Group B, which featured the two finalists from the 2010 World Cup – Spain and the Netherlands - as well as Chile and Australia". There are also phraseological units in Uzbek, which are mostly popular in the field of sports, so it is not noticeable that they have been

replaced, including units such as jonli devor, jarohatlar botqog'i, zambarakning o'qiday, metin iroda, darvozabonlar ovchisi.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

From the above examples, it became clear that the translation of phraseological units related to physical education and sports from one language to another is one of the important tasks. In this sense, we considered it permissible to touch on the methods of translating phraseological units related to the sport field during the research process. In this article, while analyzing English sports phrases and terms, we studied the characteristics of their absorption in Uzbek sports terminology and how they are used in the language. In current day, one of the important tasks of modern linguistics which is not only the classification and description of English phraseological units and terms, but also their comparative and contrastive scientific analysis and translation issues.

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